

SYSTEM AND METHOD IN PILGRIM TOURISM

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INTRODUCTION

In our country India, pilgrimage has its importance so it is very essential to manage the system of pilgrim tourism now the biggest challenge is that how to manage it and what method we can implement to make every process very smooth. There are many public charitable trusts available that sponsor the whole trip and organize the whole trip well planned. Vrindavan and Shirdi are very famous pilgrimage in India. Vrindavan is dedicated to Lord Krishna and it is situated in Uttar Pradesh, on the other hand, Shirdi is dedicated to Sai baba and it is situated in Maharashtra. All these Pilgrimages are managed by various methods created by the management of pilgrim tourism. There are many temples prevalent in India like the Mahakal Temple of Ujjain where there is a huge crowd of devotees during the Kumbh Mela. Whenever a large number of people gather for the prayers, then the management of the pilgrimage should pay special attention to the proper arrangement for all the visitors because they are here to perform various kinds of religious activities.

FACTORS AFFECTING GROWTH IN PILGRIM TOURISM

- **Authentic websites**

As we all know that nowadays people like to book hotels online whenever they want to go for vacation in the same way we can find some reliable websites on the Internet by using them we can book our room in various pilgrimage where we can stay for few days

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and can comfortably perform our rituals because we can get basic needs like food, shelter and some basic facilities.

- **Role of Travel Agents**

Travel agents help the tourists to get all the facilities in the pilgrimage because they are aware of the environment of that area. Travel agencies provide Agents who sell their product services like traveling through different mediums like bus, car, train or airplanes so accordingly one can book the ticket to go to the different pilgrimage. There may be two types of traveling one is International Travelling and another is domestic traveling for international traveling one should have a passport and other necessary documents with them and domestic traveling because it is inside the country so no need to get ready your passport.

FRAMEWORK OPERATION FOR RELIGIOUS TOURISM

Religious tourist places in India have their special importance because through this, the general public gets a little relaxed, when they come to the religious places, their mind gets purified on its own and many physical problems automatically end. Religious activists provide many services to the pilgrim tourists like accommodation and transport and its sometimes free of cost just to get blessings of many old people who don't have enough money to sponsor their trip but some kind people do this for the society and make the trip free so that people can get the benefit of meditation and can feel some kind of relaxation in their life.

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Fig. 1: Impact of Pilgrim Tourism

SOCIO-ECONOMIC EFFECT

Pilgrim Tourism affects many aspects like social and economic aspects also changes with this. it has positive as well as negative impacts on society. Some positive impacts are that due to pilgrim tourism many people get a job in religious places and through which they can survive so that it affects positively and they can generate income which helps them to perform their daily expenses.

Its gives cultural strength to our society and when people from other countries see that these people are very religious and they are involved in so many good activities this gives respect to our society and country as well and tourist from abroad also come to take advantage of this religious environment which gives us extra income for the welfare of particular pilgrimage and the area around that place.

Some negative impacts are also there such as this land cannot be used for personal reasons like you cannot do farming here and not make it residential area sometimes due to overpopulation some geographical changes also arise people come here and they make the place dirty and polluted due to unawareness of cleanliness.

ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECT

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When tourists come from various places it creates the area very crowded and the smoke of the vehicles causes a lot of air pollution. People throw food and drink items anywhere without this awareness that it can create land pollution they through plastic items into the holy rivers which makes water pollution as well and most commonly they through plastic reapers anywhere which causes land degradation.

CONCLUSION

Religious places are very important aspects of our life because whenever we feel tired from our routine life we want to go out and get some mental peace and pilgrimage is the place where we can find the real purpose of our existence. It makes us so energetic that we can re-energize ourselves within few days and can get back to our normal routine with a more positive attitude.

It allows the job for many people who are directly or indirectly attached to this business-like tour and travels, hotels, and many shops around the various pilgrimages so it's a good source of income for many people. By giving proper attention to the cleanliness of these places we can control air, water, and land pollution and can make these places the most beautiful and peaceful places in the world.

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